

CRIME

by

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ABSTRACT

Crime is an illegal act but then also done in India. Mostly ranked crimes are done in India. Every day, 100s of people killed and everyday 100s of FIR are registered for crimes.

The crimes are done on mostly in property dealing. Even though nowadays, we can't trust on our own family member or on own trustworthy persons.

Crimes is an act punishable by a state or other authority. Crimes involves violence, sex, drug's also discrimination, road rage, declared work and burglary. Crime is to harm someone or to dangerous or to intentionally to hurt someone.

Types of crimes:

1. Robbery
2. Burglary
3. cybercrime

Many think crime is a social problem. A problem as defined by society, such as homelessness, drug abuse, etc. Social root cause of crimes is:

1. Inequality
2. Not sharing power
3. Lack of support and family
4. Lack of leadership
5. Lack of awareness

Common examples for social issues:

1. Poverty and homelessness
2. Overpopulation
3. Civil right and racial discrimination
4. Gender inequality
5. Health care availability
6. Childhood obesity

INTRODUCTION

In ordinary language, a crime is an unlawful act punishable by a state or other authority. The term does not in modern criminal law, have any simple and universally accepted definition.

Nowadays crime is offence in laws. Crime deals with unlawful act or illegal act which gives fear to people and also promote to decreasing of population rate. By crimes over around 100 people dies every day. Everyday new case and new crimes registered over every state or in court every day a new news or a new type of crimes comes and we the people listen the about the crimes even the state or government court don't do anything about crimes. The modern time crimes are for small point of view or on small view of opinion as we all know about laws and Acts but the people don't take that seriously and the government also don't want to deal with this awareness which is a very important term or very important topic is there in a society. Many consider crime as a social problem A problem as defined by society, such as homelessness, drug abuse etc. Social root causes of crime are inequalities, not sharing of power, lack of support of families and neighbourhood, real or perceived inaccessibility to services, lack of leadership in communities, low value placed on children and individual well-being, the overexposure to television as a means of recreation.

Some of the social issue examples are Poverty, unemployment, unequal opportunity, racism, and malnutrition are some examples of social problems. Some of substandard housing, employment discrimination, and child abuse and neglect. By a small way of conflict, the crimes are done in higher range. Currently, the people is selfish because pf own need resources the people are killing and doing crimes. The government should have strict laws regulation and Acts for doing crimes. The government should control ion crimes by making laws and regulation Acts etc.

Usually, to be classified as a crime “The act of doing something criminal” ACTUS REUS must with exception – ‘be accompanied by the intention to do something criminal’ MENS REA.

WHAT ARE THE EXAMPLES OF A CRIME?

- Violence
- Sex or drugs
- Road rage
- Cybercrimes
- Youth crimes
- Human smuggling and human trafficking
- Fraud
- Trespass to property
- Illegal work
- Undeclared workers
- Theft
- Crimes at travellers
- Robbery

The most crime committed is in 2020 property crime was the most common type of crime committed.

JUVENILES DELINQUENCY

Juvenile means a person who is very young teenager, adolescent or underage. In other words, juvenile means children who have not yet reached to age of adults in the sense that they are still childish or immature.

Legally speaking a juvenile can be defined as a child who has not attained a certain age at which he can be held liable for his criminal acts like an adult person under the law of the country.

Juvenile is a child who is alleged to have committed certain acts or omission which are in violation of any law and are declared to be an offence. In terms of law a juvenile is a person who has not attained the age of 18 years.

- **CRIMES AGAINST A PERSON**

Crimes against a person are those that resulted in physical or mental harm to another person. Such as assault or battery, arson, child abuse, domestic abuse, domestic violences, kidnappings, rape and statutory rape.

- **CRIMES AGAINST PROPERTY**

Crimes against property typically involve interference with the property of another party although, it also involves physical or mental harm to another person. Such as theft, robbery, auto theft, burglary etc.

LIST OF AMENDING LEGISLATION ACT:

1. THE CODE OF CRIMINAL PROCEDURE, 1882
2. THE INDIAN PENAL CODE ,1860
3. CIVIL PROCEDURE CODE,1908
4. INDIAN CRIMINAL LAW AMENDMENT ACT, 1895

CLASSIFICATION OF CRIMES

Some writers have preferred to classify the crimes under following:

1. LEGAL CRIMES

That can be termed as traditional crimes such as theft, robber, rape, etc.

2. POLITICAL OFFENDERS

Are those which are motivated poetically or committed in violation of election laws or norms set out for the political in course of their political activities.

3. ECONOMICS CRIMES

In these includes professional crimes such as white-collar offences, tax evasion, smuggling, etc.

4. SOCIAL CRIMES

Social crimes are those which are committed under social legislation such as Dowry Prohibition Act, Immoral Traffic Protection Act, Child Marriage Restrain Act, etc.

5. All other remaining crimes which are committed under the local and special laws are as miscellaneous crimes. E.g., Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, Drugs Act.

However, under Indian Penal Code the offences have been classified into 7 broad categories:

1. Offences against Person like Murder, Hurt, etc
2. Offences against Property like Theft, Robbery, etc
3. Offences related to Documents like Forgery, Cheating, etc
4. Offences against Public Tranquillity like Unlawful Assembly.
5. Offences against State like waging war against the state.

6. Offences related to Public Servant like preventing services of summons or other proceedings or threat of injury to public servants.
7. Offences related to Marriage like Adultery, cruelty, bigamy.

PUNISHMENTS UNDER IPC

Section 53 of the Indian Penal Code ,1860 prescribes 5 kinds of punishments.

1. Death Penalty
2. Life imprisonment
3. Imprisonment
 - Rigorous
 - Simple
4. Forfeiture of property
5. Fine

DEATH PENALTY

Death penalty is also called the capital punishment. Under this punishment, a person is hanged till he dies. The infliction of death sentence or taking away the offender's life by authority as a punishment for an offence is capital punishment or death penalty. In India it is rare to give punishment like this.

Punishment in the following offences:

- a) Waging war against the Government of India (Sec. 121)
- b) Abetting Mutually actually committed (Sec.132)
- c) Giving and fabricating false evidence upon which an innocent (Sec. 194)
- d) Murder (Sec.302)
- e) Murder by Life convicts (Sec. 303)

- f) Abetment of suicide of a minor or an insane or intoxicated person. (Sec.305)
- g) Dacoity accompanied with murder (Sec.396)
- h) Kidnapping for Ransom (Sec.364A)

LIFE IMPRISONMENT

The words imprisonment for life was substituted for transportation for life by Act XXVI of 1995. In its ordinary connotation imprisonment for life means imprisonment for whole of the whole of the remaining life period of the convicted person's natural death. According to sec 57 imprisonment for life shall be reckoned as equivalent to imprisonment for 20 years. But only for calculating fractions of terms of punishment imprisonment for life shall be reckoned as equivalent to imprisonment for 20 years.

IMPRISONMENT

Imprisonment means taking away a person's freedom and putting him in prison.

Acc. To sec 53 of IPC 2 kinds of punishment:

1. **Simple:** It is a punishment in which the offender is confined to jail only and not subjected to any hard labour.

Some are punishment in simple imprisonment:

- Wrongful restraint sec 341
- Uttering any word or making any sound or gesture with an intention to insult the modesty of a women sec 509
- Defamation sec 500,501,502
- Misconduct in public place by a drunken person sec 510

2. **Rigorous:** The offender is put to hard labour such as grinding corn, digging, cutting wood etc. The following are some offences which are punishable:

- Kidnapping in order to murder sec 364
- Robbery sec 392
- Dacoity sec 395
- House robbery in order to commit offence with death sec 449

FORFEITURE OF PROPERTY

Forfeiture implies the loss of property of the accused. Under this punishment, the state seizes the property of a criminal. It is the result of the wrong or default caused by the person. The property forfeited may be movable or immovable.

Two provisions of forfeiture of the property has been abolished:

- Under sec 126 for committing depredation on territories of power at peace with government of India.
- Under sec 127 for receiving property taken during war or depredation mentioned in sec 126 IPC.

FINE:

Fine can be simply defined as monetary punishment. Almost all section related with awarding punishment includes fine as punishment. However, section 63 says where sum is expressed to which a fine may extended, the amount of fine to which the offender is liable is unlimited, but shall not be excessive.

